

Table 1. Yield potential of Zhefu No. 9 in regional tests in eastern and central China, 1991.

Site	Average		Maximum	
	Yield (t/ha)	Increase over check (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase over check (%)
Hangzhou, Zhejiang	6.3	8.1 ^a	8.8	15.2 ^a
Ninbo, Zhejiang	6.9	10.4 ^a	8.1	4.3 ^a
Linhai, Zhejiang	5.8	7.7 ^a	7.7	10.2 ^a
Wuzhou, Jiangxi	6.8	10.5 ^a	7.7	12.6 ^a
Shangrao, Jiangxi	6.5	6.2 ^a	7.8	11.5 ^a
Changsha, Hunan	7.0	18.7 ^b	8.0	20.1 ^b
Yuyang, Hunan	7.1	10.2 ^b	8.6	18.3 ^b
Wuhan, Hubei	6.5	14.7 ^b	7.5	18.9 ^b

^aErjiufong. ^bZhefu No. 802.

Table 2. Morphoagronomic characters of Zhefu No. 9 at different sites in central and eastern China, 1992.

Character	Hangzhou, Zhejiang	Wuzhou, Jiangxi	Xiangtan, Hunan	Wuhan, Hubei
Plant height (cm)	81.0	74.5	85.0	88.0
Panicle length (cm)	18.3	18.1	19.4	21.0
Grains (no./panicle)	100.5	102.4	124.0	129.0
Fertility (%)	78.0	83.6	86.5	78.6
1,000 grain wt (g)	22.6	22.9	22.0	22.8

respectively (Table 1). It is highly resistant to rice blast under field conditions. (See Table 2 for morphoagronomic characters.)

It has medium grain and good cooking quality, with an amylose content of 23.1%. ■

Xin Guang S, a promising photoperiod/temperature-sensitive genic male sterile (P/TGMS) line for two-line system of hybrid rice breeding

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Seed set of bagged panicles of Xin Guang S grown in the phytotron, CNRRI, Fuyang, China. 1992.

Temperature ^a (°C)	Daylength ^b (h/d)	Plants observed (no.)	Seed set of bagged panicle (%)
30.1	15.0	15	0 ± 0
	14.0	15	0 ± 0
	12.5	15	0 ± 0
24.1	15.0	15	0.67 ± 1.44
	14.0	15	0.22 ± 0.58
	12.5	15	57.33 ± 10.75
23.1	15.0	15	1.30 ± 2.76
	14.0	15	9.43 ± 9.49
	12.5	15	23.15 ± 13.54

^aTemperature was weighted mean of 1 d. ^bIllumination time: 12.5 h, 0600-1830 h; 14.0 h, 0530-1930 h; 15.0 h, 0500-2000 h.

We developed a P/TGMS rice from a spontaneous male sterile segregant found in the F₂ population of cross 2490(indica)/Geng 3 (japonica)/MR365(indica).

To observe agronomic traits, outcrossing habits, and fertility alteration, Xin Guang S was sown every 10 d from 9 Apr to 4 Jul 1993 at Hangzhou and transplanted 30 d later at one plant/hill at 15 × 16.6 cm. Fertility was estimated by the seed set of bagged panicles. To identify photoperiod/temperature response, transplanted seedlings with five fully extended leaves were transferred into the phytotron at the China National Rice Research Institute (CNRRI) in 1992 and grown to ripening phase under different photoperiod/temperature settings.

Panicles of 15 plants were bagged at anthesis, and seed set was evaluated for each photoperiod/temperature treatment.

Growth duration of Xin Guang S from sowing to 20% heading varied from 80 to 102 d, depending on sowing date. Xin Guang S was about 85 cm tall with about 10 tillers/plant, white stigmas, and a 74.8% exertion rate.

Xin Guang S had complete and stable sterility with the typical abortion of pollen grains and no seed set before 25 Aug. After this time it exhibited high to partial sterility and then partial fertility from 15 to 25 Sep, during which time very few pollen grains were aborted, although seed set of bagged panicles was 16.1-25.1%.

In the phytotron, Xin Guang S showed complete sterility at high temperatures (30.1° C) regardless of daylength. At low temperatures (23.1-24.1° C), it showed high sterility under long daylength (14-15 h/d) and partial fertility under short daylength (12.5 h/d). Xin Guang S is therefore photoperiod-sensitive (see table).

Extensive testcrossing showed that hybrids had normal fertility when Xin Guang S was crossed with indica and japonica rice, suggesting that it is a potentially promising P/TGMS line for the two-line system of hybrid rice breeding. ■